

High-Power LEDs for Optical Wireless V2V Links

High-Flux VLC Emitters with Spectrally Tailored LED Drive in Support of Simple Baseband Signaling

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Abstract:

Visible light communication (VLC) is an attractive way to integrate data exchange in systems that are merely dedicated to lighting. As the arguably most abundant luminaire, the light emitting diode (LED) can contribute to this challenge as a low-cost light emitter. A multi-faceted approach is evaluated to overcome its intrinsic bandwidth/flux trade-off, including analogue equalization, spectral stitching and incoherent beam combining. An optical link budget of 33 dB is found to be compatible at 100 Mb/s data rate, as it is evidenced through low-latency Ethernet-over-VLC transmission over medium- and high-flux (>50 lm) LEDs, proving further that a sub-20 lm LED can cater for the real-time point-cloud transmission over a 100-m out-door VLC link. The migration to Gb/s-class VLC rates is accomplished through laser-based emitters and a strongly pre-equalized LED drive. The results reveal that broadband modulation with simple data coding still prevails over distortion-sensitive modulation, while analogue pre-equalization techniques for 1-Gb/s transmission over low-complexity LED emitters are required to enter a costly trade-off between wideband support and a highly reduced optical link budget.

I. Introduction

Spectral scarcity in radio frequency (RF) based wireless access has made optical wireless communications (OWC) an attractive alternative. Besides being a license-free wireless technology, OWC can capitalize on its robustness to electro-magnetic interference and thus on its compatibility with high user densities. Its application space ranges from in-door deployments [1,2] to point-to-point free-space optical backhaul links [3,4] and scenarios including mobile users [5,6]. The abundance of light emitting diodes (LED) in consumer applications renders them ideal candidates for low-cost implementations of visible-light communications (VLC) [7]. Towards this, LEDs have proven their versatile use as luminaire, joint emitter / transmitter for simultaneous illumination and communication [8], and even as photodetector [9,10]. The electro-optic bandwidth becomes the most pertinent performance parameter of a LED for an adoption of VLC functionality, while a high luminous flux is required at the same time when lighting has to be supported.

However, there is a trade-off between the native LED bandwidth B and flux Φ , as indicated through state-of-the-art works summarized in Fig. 1. This limitation renders a universal LED-based lighting and communication emitter infeasible and instead suggests a careful choice of LED type according to the actual application setting. For example, micro-LEDs offer large electro-optic bandwidths in the GHz range [11-21], which can be beneficial for low-cost board-level or wired data interconnects. Their predominant short-wavelength emission characteristics in the ultra-violet to blue region results in a low luminous flux of less than 0.1 lm. This greatly limits their applicability to in-door VLC where luminaries shall be jointly used for lighting. However, first demonstrations of micro-LEDs in the green region [11, 14, 15, 19, 20] and phosphor-based white micro-LEDs [22] have proven native bandwidths in the 500 – 1300 MHz range. Standard surface-mounted LED devices with moderate flux characteristics <10 lm strike a balance between the performance credentials sought for joint lighting and communication [23-27]. Even though their native bandwidths are typically confined to a range between 100 – 500 MHz, Gb/s data rates can be supported through an equalized channel response or digital signal processing (DSP) assisted multi-carrier modulation formats. An alternative can be the use of superluminescent diodes, which combine the advantages of LEDs and laser diodes (LD). For these, a higher native electro-optic bandwidth of 405 MHz has been shown [28].

The ideal emitter candidate would be a high-power LED. However, high-flux LEDs (>10 lm) are subject to an intrinsic bandwidth limitation as they face larger junction depletion and diffusion capacitances due to its large-area die. Together with bonding parasitics and the series resistance introduced due to ohmic LED contacts, the electro-optic response is typically characterized by a steep roll-off after a few MHz [29], meaning a rapid drop in modulation bandwidth. The dashed line in Fig. 1 interrelates with this bandwidth limitation by highlighting a constant $B \cdot \sqrt{\Phi}$ product. While white-LED systems [30-36] face an intrinsically slower response due to phosphor-based light conversion, research works on single-color high-power LEDs [37-44] have shown 3.4 Gb/s VLC over a blue LED with a power of 93 mW. This was achieved after applying excessive analogue

equalization with a large dynamic pre-distortion range of more than 25 dB to obtain an end-to-end VLC bandwidth of 730 MHz [39]. Nevertheless, this result proves that VLC applications can be sustained even in the high-flux lighting segment.

The present work extends an initial study [45] on the trade-off that resides between providing either a high luminous flux or a high bandwidth for a practical VLC emitter. Simple on-off keyed (OOK) data transmission is supported over elevated VLC link budgets of up to 33 dB through a combination of frequency-stitched data transmission, analogue equalization and/or incoherent power combining in multi-element emitter configurations. The limitations of these techniques are scrutinized and comparison with laser-based emitters is made. Finally, a potential application for out-door point-cloud data transmission between road-side users is evaluated.

Fig. 1. Electro-optic bandwidth and flux of state-of-the art LED technologies.

This manuscript is organized as follows. Section II sets the scene by introducing the utilized light emitters. Section III discusses the concepts of spectral stitching and power combining for high-flux LEDs. Section IV features the experimental setup. Section V then elaborates on the VLC performance for LED- and LD-based transmitters and conducts an out-door investigation for a VLC-based relay of point-cloud data acquired through light detection and ranging (LiDAR) technology. Finally, Section VI concludes the work.

II. Characterization of High-Flux Incoherent Light Emitters

When luminaries are simultaneously used for lighting and data communication, the white composition of light deriving from a compound of blue (B), green (G) and red (R) sources provides a spectral degree of freedom since any of the constituent emitters can be used as data transmitter. Figure 2(a) presents the white-light spectrum Σ of an R/G/B emitter, together with the luminous efficacy V_λ . The coordinates in the CIE-1931 chromaticity diagram, shown in Fig. 2(b), are $x = 0.328$ and $y = 0.335$. The white-light emission Σ has a correlated color temperature C_T of 5703 K.

Two red-LED types are considered: The first is a medium-flux LED with up to 18 lm at 120 mA, denoted as LED-**M** and shown in Fig. 3(a). The second is a high-flux LED reaching 52 lm at 350 mA. This LED is denoted as LED-**H** and included in Fig. 3(b). Figure 2(a) reports the corresponding spectra (M, H) at 634 nm. Compared to the blue and green sources, the red channel provides a better overlap with the spectral response of silicon photodetectors, as it is evidenced through the red-shifted responsivity R_{APD} of an avalanche photodiode (APD) used for data reception. The following work will therefore focus on the red LEDs as VLC transmitter.

Fig. 2. (a) Optical spectra for LED- and LD-based emitters, including (b) their chromaticity and (c) VLI characteristics.

Comparison will be further made with a red laser diode (LD), whose spectrum L is centered at 638.1 nm (Fig. 2(a)). The voltage-light-current (VLI) characteristics of high-power LEDs and LD are discussed in Fig. 2(c). Even though the high-flux LED-H (H) shows a clear advantage in terms of launched optical power, its incoherent light emission impacts the efficiency when collimating the light beam. For this reason, the optical power in Fig. 2(c), which was acquired using a free-space powermeter, is reduced when compared to its nominal flux of 52 lm at 350 mA. Even though the red laser (L) features an output of up to 19 mW and could therefore potentially enable a high optical link budget by virtue of coherent light emission, eye safety considerations have to be applied for the launched pencil beam of the VLC transmitter.

Fig. 3. VLC transmitter based on (a) power combining and (b) spectral stitching.

III. Spectrally Stitched Bandwidth Extension vs. Combination of Lower-Flux Beams

Each of the proposed VLC transmitters builds on three LED emitters that are bonded through incoherent power combining. Depending on the flux rating, the LED elements of the VLC transmitter are either driven by the same data signal (LED-M) or by the respective band of a frequency-stitched signal (LED-H). In both cases, the modulating signal falls within a flat region of its electro-optic response. Both approaches are conceptually sketched in Fig. 3.

Figure 3(a) depicts the situation where the electro-optic response of a LED provides a sufficiently wide bandwidth to accommodate a baseband data signal that is encoded through simple OOK. This case will apply to LED-M, where multiple LED emitters can then leverage on the compound flux that is emitted by the VLC transmitter in order to address the flux limitation of a single element by means of power combining.

In case that the modulation response of the LED is not fast enough, as shown in Fig. 3(b) and applicable to LED-H, a spectral decomposition of the electrical baseband data signal into multiple concatenated frequency bands can provide a sufficiently wide bandwidth, provided that the electro-optic response of the “slow” LED elements features a smooth roll-off. This prerequisite applies to several LED examples of Fig. 1 as they feature a 6-dB bandwidth f_{6dB} that extends well beyond their 3-dB bandwidth f_{3dB} . For a constant roll-off and $f_{6dB} \geq 2f_{3dB}$, the effective 3-dB bandwidth of a stitched electro-optic VLC transmitter response can be extended to at least $N \cdot f_{3dB}$ when employing N high-flux LEDs, as sketched in Fig. 3(b). Given this spectrally concatenated response that is emphasized as ξ in Fig. 3(b), simple OOK modulation can be again used in combination with analogue filtering embedded in the driver circuitry. It shall be further noted that the spectral decomposition of a data signal towards multiple individual driving signals can be accomplished through simple lowpass and bandpass filtering of the same data signal.

Figure 4(a) presents the response functions of 21 LED-M samples. There is a good overlap in the frequency-dependent functions, as indicated in the histogram for the 3-dB bandwidth presented in Fig. 4(b). The average bandwidth is 22.15 MHz, with a peak-to-peak deviation of 6.5 MHz. The deviation in the electro-optic response from the average performance is reported in Fig. 4(c), which shows the accumulative histogram for this deviation of the modulation response over three frequency bands of interest. These bands cover a frequency range that (i) stops just below the 3-dB bandwidth, (ii) is allocated just after and (iii) well beyond this 3-dB bandwidth. There is a very similar performance at the lower frequency range up to 20 MHz, where 95% of the response functions fall within a small deviation of ± 0.45 dB. This value increases up to ± 0.87 dB for the mid-frequency roll-off range between 20 and 50 MHz, and up to ± 1.36 dB at higher frequencies above 50 MHz, which are well beyond the 3-dB bandwidth of the LED.

Fig. 4. (a) Variation in electro-optic response of LED-M samples.

(b) Histogram of 3-dB bandwidth and

(c) deviation of electro-optic responses from the average performance.

Given the similarity in modulation response and its rather smooth roll-off, a simple and common analogue equalizer (AEQ) design can be in principle applied to all LED-M emitters to extend the VLC emitter bandwidth. This also holds for LED-H, which

requires an AEQ that is adapted to a lower electro-optic 3-dB bandwidth of 15 MHz. Nonetheless, a second AEQ design with a more pronounced equalization response will be applied additionally to investigate the possibility of obtaining an enhanced emitter bandwidth.

Figure 5 reports the native (\square, \circ) and equalized ($\blacksquare, \bullet, \blacktriangledown$) responses of both LED types when using AEQs with moderate and strong equalization, herein referred to as Type-I and Type-II AEQ, respectively. The architectures of these AEQs are appended to Fig. 5. The AEQs introduce a frequency-dependent pre-equalization of 12-15 dB (Type-I) and up to 28 dB (Type-II) at the lower frequency range. The “smoother” Type-I AEQ extends the bandwidth to 37 (\blacksquare , LED-H) and 77 MHz (\bullet , LED-M) at the expense of the aforementioned RF losses. However, this loss vs. bandwidth trade-off is beneficial since extra gain can be easily accommodated before the RF driver stage. In case of LED-M, the equalized modulation response already suits 100 Mb/s modulation. LED-H will instead resort to a stitched response (\blacktriangle), which is introduced as ξ in Fig. 5. With this, the bandwidth can be virtually extended to 87 MHz by offsetting the roll-off in the equalized electro-optic response of LED-H (\blacksquare) at the two frequencies $f_1 = 25$ MHz and $f_2 = 50$ MHz.

Fig. 5. Native and equalized electro-optic responses of high-flux LEDs and LD, and NEP characteristics of the VLC receivers.

The bandwidth of LED-M can be extended to 746 MHz (\blacktriangledown) through the Type-II AEQ. This makes it suitable for data transmission at 1 Gb/s. However, the huge RF loss introduced not only requires a high gain to compensate, but also limits the optical modulation amplitude since the saturation power of the RF driver has to remain at a reasonable level while higher frequency components still face a significant loss in response after this RF driving stage. Moreover, a higher dynamic range needs to be accounted for during RF signal drive.

Figure 5 further shows the response of the visible red LD (L) as an alternative Gb/s-class VLC transmitter candidate. The native electro-optic 3-dB bandwidth of the red LD is 1.45 GHz (\diamond) and an extension to 1.96 GHz is possible through addition of a Type-I AEQ (\blacklozenge).

IV. Experimental Setup

Figure 6 shows the setup for evaluating the VLC performance in terms of compatible optical budget for the two transmitter configurations based on high-power LED and visible-wavelength LD technologies. In the following, the optical budget is to be understood as the optical excess loss that is inserted into a lab-scale free-space VLC link that has been set for optimal coupling between its transmitter and receiver.

The multi-element VLC transmitter features either three red LEDs or a compound of fiber-coupled cyan/green/red LDs, whose outputs are combined by means of a visible-light wavelength division multiplexer (WDM). AEQs are included within the electrical driver path. The optical signals are launched and collimated by a 2" lens. Neutral density (ND) filters are employed to set the optical loss of the lab-scale (6.5 m) link between VLC transmitter and receiver. This enables an investigation of the compatible optical budget for VLC.

An equivalent reach can then be estimated for each of the emitter types, following the relation of optical budget versus link reach that is presented in Fig. 7 for the two beam propagation characteristics of collimated LED- and LD-based light emission. While the widening in beam spot diameter (\times, \blacklozenge) has been acquired through direct measurement over distance, the optical VLC budget that results from the beam widening has been calculated according to the geometric loss when considering 2" lens optics at the VLC receiver to increase its collection efficiency. The superior collimation of the LD (\blacklozenge) is clearly advantageous to overcome a large free-space optical reach, while a large budget of ~ 30 dB applies to LED-based VLC when a reach of 100 m is considered (\circ).

Fig. 6. Experimental setup for in-door VLC transmission using LED- and LD-based emitters. The insets show the LiDAR used for the out-door experiment and the RSSI monitor at the VLC receiver.

The VLC receiver builds on an APD that is co-integrated with a transimpedance amplifier (TIA). Its active diameter of $\Phi_{\text{APD}} = 200 \mu\text{m}$ and a high multiplication corresponding to a responsivity of $\sim 33 \text{ A/W}$ strike a balance with low receiver noise. The actual noise performance is characterized in Fig. 5. It shows a noise equivalent power (NEP) of $< 80 \text{ fW/}\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. In case of the higher bandwidth supported by the LD, a 10G PIN/TIA has been employed as alternative VLC receiver to investigate wide-band modulation scenarios.

Data transmission is evaluated through waveform signals that are generated by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG). The AWG drives the three LED emitter elements with identical or specific waveforms in case of incoherent power combining and spectral stitching, respectively (1, 3 in Fig. 6). Direct testing of the bit error ratio (BER) has been conducted for OOK transmission, while orthogonally frequency division multiplexed (OFDM) data transmission is demodulated and evaluated off-line after acquisition through a real-time oscilloscope. Moreover, Ethernet traffic has been used as an alternative data source by extracting drive signals by means of protocol termination. For this, the optical signal of an Ethernet switch is re-converted into an electrical drive to feed a single emitter element (2, 4). After photoreception, an electrical limiter regenerates the detected Ethernet frame before it is re-converted to an optical signal through an auxiliary LD, which directly feeds the Ethernet switch at the receiver side. The uplink return channel that serves discovery and packet acknowledgement as a requirement to establish an Ethernet connection is facilitated through multimode OM4 fiber (ϵ). The Ethernet throughput over the VLC link is then evaluated by generating artificial traffic to probe the link.

Fig. 7. Acquired beam spot diameter and optical budget for free-space VLC transmission using a LED- and LD-based light emitter.

V. Evaluation of VLC Transmission Performance

In the following, the transmission performance is discussed for LED- and LD-based VLC transmitters. Direct Ethernet-over-VLC transmission is further evaluated for an out-door link.

A. LED-based VLC link performance

Figure 8(a) reports the BER performance over the optical budget introduced in excess to the lab-scale VLC link, for which ND filters emulate extra link loss (or reach). Results further relate to the use of the Type-I AEQ. The VLC transmitter comprising of three baseband-modulated LED-M emitters supports a high optical budget of 32.9 dB (●) before the BER degrades to below 10^{-9} . An improvement of 4.2 dB is obtained when compared to a single LED-M emitter (○), as it can be expected for triple-beam combining. With this, a tentative VLC reach of 157 m can be supported (Fig. 7, ○).

Fig. 8. (a) BER performance of LED-based VLC transmission when employing a Type-I AEQ and spectral stitching in case of LED-H. (b) Sensitivity to receiver misalignment. (c) Ethernet-over-VLC streaming, including LED- and LD-based emitters.

In case of the frequency-stitched data transmission through a VLC transmitter that involves three LED-H emitters, an optical budget of 21.3 dB can be accomplished at a BER of 10^{-9} (■). Despite the larger luminous flux, the supported budget is considerably lower when compared to the power-combined transmitter based on three LED-M emitters. This is explained by the sensitivity of the stitching process to non-linear distortions and filtering effects, which also requires the driver circuitry to operate in its back-off regime. In this way, saturation effects are avoided, yet at the result of a lower optical modulation amplitude and therefore with a penalty concerning the supported optical budget for the VLC link. Towards this, Figure 9 shows the received RF spectrum and eye diagrams for frequency-stitched transmission. The three individual bands are delimited at f_1 and f_2 , as introduced in Fig. 3(b) through $f_{3\text{dB}}$ and $f_{6\text{dB}}$. While none of the individual bands (i.e., single LED-H emitters) yields a useful optical representation of the input data signal since these bands solely resemble a specific spectral portion of the overall signal drive, the sum of all bands (i.e., all LED-H outputs) represents the transmitted 100 Mb/s OOK signal with a clearly open eye. Yet, this eye is noisier when compared to the power-combined LED-M transmission with intrinsically flat response since the analogue driving signals resulting from band filtering are more sensitive to non-linearity introduced by RF amplification. Therefore, a VLC transmitter based on LED-H emitters would be required to overprovision its RF drive capability, which due to the large current swing of the high-flux LEDs becomes techno-economically challenging.

The sensitivity of the reception to a misalignment between VLC transmitter and receiver is discussed in Fig. 8(b), which shows the BER as a function of optical budget and angular misalignment α of the receiver. When the beam spot is optimally focused on the APD receiver through the receiver optics, meaning that its active area is optimally illuminated, a BER of 10^{-9} is accomplished for a narrow field-of-view (FoV) of $2\alpha = 0.55^\circ$ (●). A wider FoV can be supported when the received beam is deliberately defocused to widen its spot diameter at the plane of the active photodetector area, at the expense of sub-optimal light coupling. In this way, the acceptance angle 2α increases to 1.75° and 3.4° for spot diameters of 2 (▲) and 5 mm, respectively. The penalty Π in supported optical budget then becomes 6.9 (▲) and 12.2 dB. This would relate to a reduced VLC reach of 69 and 23 m (Fig. 7), respectively. A wider FoV should be therefore enabled through multi-element VLC receiver architectures [46, 47], which can greatly mitigate this unfavourable compromise in optical link budget. Nonetheless, the requirement of having wide FoV might not apply, given OWC applications that aim at an extended VLC link reach for which a wide FoV is of secondary or no pressing importance.

Fig. 9. Stitched data signal received after VLC transmission through a compound of three LED-H emitters.

Moreover, 100 Mb/s Ethernet data has been streamed over the VLC link based on a single LED-M emitter. Figure 8(c) presents the resulting data rate R that was transmitted over the optical link with a power margin of 1 dB to its 10^{-9} reception sensitivity over a duration of more than one hour. Apart from a few isolated drops in rate, which occur for 0.13% of the logged measurements, there was no stability concern raised for this simplified LED-based VLC link. The drop δ in data rate at the very beginning of the measurement results from a deliberate blocking of the beam by a moving object.

Fig. 10 relates the transmission performances of a single LED-M emitter when applying either the Type-I or Type-II AEQ. Taking the previously discussed 100-Mb/s transmitter performance with Type-I AEQ (o) as a baseline, a similar BER performance is achieved with the Type-II equalizer (\bullet). This can be expected due to the mere introduction of a spectrally flat AEQ loss together with RF re-amplification. When advancing the data rate to 1 Gb/s (\blacktriangle) by virtue of the equalized LED-M response (\blacktriangledown in Fig. 5), an open eye is again obtained. Even though low BER values $< 10^{-9}$ can be accomplished, the supported VLC link budget shows a tolerable excess loss of < 2 dB in addition to the established lab link. Compared to the performance at 100 Mb/s (\bullet), the offset in reception sensitivity is more than 10 dB, as it could be inferred from the mere difference in data rates. This extra penalty is explained by the reduced optical modulation amplitude for the 1 Gb/s signal, which is a result of the finite saturation power when using the same RF driver before the LED emitter. Here, the RF swing of the high-frequency components towards 1 GHz of the pre-equalized signal, whose eye diagram has been appended as Fig. 10(b), is facing an upper limit that is determined by the saturation characteristics of the RF driver. Since the response of the LED emitter is very low at high frequencies, the overall optical modulation amplitude is reduced with respect to the use of a Type-I AEQ. This inevitably results in a rate-corrected reception penalty of 16.8 dB for 1-Gb/s VLC transmission (\blacktriangle) after accounting for the 10-dB difference in data rates. Nonetheless, these results prove the use of a single LED-M emitter for 1 Gb/s OOK transmission. A VLC emitter with Type-II AEQ could be employed in a rate-adaptive manner, where its transmission bandwidth is adjusted according to the actual VLC reach.

Fig. 10. (a) BER performance for 1 Gb/s VLC transmission over single LED-M emitter when employing a Type-II AEQ. (b) Pre-equalized waveform for 1 Gb/s VLC transmission.

B. Laser-based VLC link performance

The VLC link can be enriched by laser sources and DSP if a higher degree of complexity can be tolerated. The following investigates such a link configuration. First, a single red LD has been employed as VLC transmitter. Since its coherent light can be collimated in a more efficient way (Fig. 7, \blacklozenge) compared to the previous LED emitters, a higher reach can be accommodated for the same optical budget. The launch power has been restricted to 1 mW to adhere to eye-safety limits.

The BER performance for 1.25 Gb/s OOK transmission is presented in Fig. 11(a) for APD-based (\blacksquare) and PIN-based (\bullet) photoreception. A BER of 10^{-10} is accomplished at an optical budget of 28 and 11.2 dB, respectively. Even though the PIN/TIA receiver does not offer the same multiplicative gain as the APD/TIA, it can already accommodate for a high VLC reach beyond 100 m thanks to the well-collimated pencil beam (Fig. 7). Moreover, it enables higher data rates due to its extended opto-electronic bandwidth in combination with the improved electro-optic response of LDs. Towards this, Fig. 11(a) further shows the BER for 2.5 Gb/s transmission (\blacktriangle), for which an optical budget of 6.9 dB is obtained.

Moreover, long-term GbE transmission has been evaluated for this VLC setting. Figure 8(c) presents the corresponding data rate over a duration of one hour. The average rate is 922 Mb/s. No rate drops have been noticed.

When considering multi-carrier modulation, the data rate can be adapted to the actual budget of the VLC link. This is demonstrated in Fig. 11(b), which presents the supported data rate after forward error correction (FEC) for OFDM transmission using the APD- (\circ, \triangle) and PIN-based ($\bullet, \blacktriangle, \blacklozenge$) VLC receiver. Results are shown for modulation of 128 sub-carriers over various OFDM bandwidths that range from 1.25 to 2.5 GHz, according to the modulation response of the LD (Fig. 5). For the more sensitive APD/TIA receiver, an optical budget of 28.8 dB can be achieved for 1.25 Gb/s transmission. This aligns well to the sensitivity obtained for simple OOK transmission. However, the modulation can be tailored to the actual link conditions by means of adaptive bit loading, which allows to optimize the supported data rate over the VLC link. For example, a data rate of up to 3.9 Gb/s can be supported (\triangle), though at a reduced budget of 20 dB. Here, the limited reception bandwidth of the APD/TIA and its saturation towards lower optical budgets imposes an upper limit for the data rate. On the other hand, the PIN/TIA receiver supports up to 9 Gb/s (\blacklozenge) at a reduced optical budget of 4 dB, by virtue of sub-carrier modulation with up to 64-point quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), as inserted in Fig. 11(b).

Fig. 11. (a) BER performance of LD-based VLC using OOK. (b) Supported rate when adopting multi-carrier modulation. (c) EVM for spectrally bonded OFDM transmission over cyan/green/red wavelength channels.

A stitched transmission methodology is thinkable to further extend the data rate. Towards this direction, spectral bonding has been investigated in the wavelength domain, using cyan (494 nm), green (520 nm) and red (638 nm) LDs. This is to avoid cross-talk effects that would arise when using coherent light emitters with the same operating wavelengths, especially when considering uncooled LD operation. Three independent OFDM signals with adaptive bit loading were used to modulate these LDs, using OFDM bandwidths of 1, 1 and 2 GHz, respectively. Again, the aggregated optical power launched by the VLC transmitter has been limited to 1 mW. Figure 12 shows the signal spectrum after photoreception with the PIN/TIA receiver. The three wavelength channels can be discerned through the three RF bands and the pilot tone that has been added at the spectral center of the respective OFDM signals. The error vector magnitude (EVM) after reception of the three tributary bands is reported in Fig. 11(c). The red VLC channel clearly performs best, as it allows sub-carriers to be modulated with up to 32-QAM, even at a higher OFDM bandwidth. For an optical budget of 3 dB, the spectral channels contribute with post-FEC data rates of 1.73 (cyan), 2.4 (green) and 6.07 (red) Gb/s. This favoring of the longer red wavelength is attributed to the responsivity of the

PIN/TIA receiver, which follows a silicon-dominated response curve, similarly as shown in Fig. 2(a). Nonetheless, a bonded post-FEC data rate of 10.2 Gb/s can be accomplished. An advantage over the single-channel transmission in Fig. 11(b) is nevertheless spoiled by the responsivity cut-off towards the blue spectrum, which would require blue-enhanced receivers.

Fig. 12. Spectrally bonded spectrum received for triple-band OFDM transmission over LD-based VLC receiver.

C. Out-door Ethernet-over-VLC relay of LiDAR point-clouds using a sub-20 lumen LED

Finally, VLC transmission has been embedded in a road-side scenario where LiDAR data is sourced and transmitted between two road-side users (RSU) to enable local data fusion. In this experiment, raw LiDAR point-cloud data is transparently streamed over a 100 Mb/s Ethernet link that is established over a VLC channel with a reach of 102 m between two stationary RSUs, as highlighted in Fig. 13(a).

The same VLC methodology as in Fig. 6 has been applied: A LED-based VLC transmitter is employed at RSU1. It builds on a single LED-M emitter, which sources its Ethernet data from a 16-channel rotating multi-beam LiDAR (Velodyne VLP-16). This LiDAR operates at 903 nm and has a vertical field-of-view of 30°. It transmits its point-cloud data through (downlink) UDP packets over the VLC link for subsequent fusion with local LiDAR data at RSU2. The optical signal received through the APD/TIA at RSU2 is tracked through a received signal strength indicator (RSSI) that monitors the 100 MbE signaling during link detection / negotiation to assist the alignment of the VLC receiver. The chosen configuration for the optical link supports a low-latency data relay by virtue of the fully analogue VLC layout and simple OOK modulation. This is especially critical in view of applications targeting data fusion to support automotive localization and mapping.

The out-door evaluation of the VLC link has been conducted at a parking space that is located between three buildings, denoted as B1-B3 in Fig. 13(a). The measurements have been conducted during a morning in early summer at a background illuminance of 4200 lx. Figure 13(b) shows the fused point cloud at RSU2 that is expanded by the LiDAR data from RSU1, which has been conveyed over the VLC link. There is no sector lost during the VLC transmission of acquired LiDAR point-cloud data, as it is evidenced by the continuous angular acquisition of objects around RSU1. This enables RSU2 to clearly discern remote features in the vicinity of RSU1, such as the exemplarily highlighted objects denoted as **B** (bar gate at the entrance of parking space), **C** (parked car), **D** (front wall of storage building) and **E** (truck passing by on road). This proves that a single high-flux LED can cater for the relay of raw point-cloud data over a 100-m VLC channel.

Fig. 13. (a) LED-based VLC relay of LiDAR point clouds from RSU1 to the data fusion point at RSU2. (b) Resulting point cloud as perceived by RSU2 and relation of characteristic points A-D to the local environment.

VI. Conclusion

Bandwidth enhancement has been evaluated for high-flux LEDs, including spectral stitching and analogue equalization with high dynamic range. Even though high-flux (>50 lm) LEDs have been shown to support 100 Mb/s transmission, the higher linearity required to accomplish accurate stitching in the RF domain renders them less efficient than medium-flux LEDs with power-combined OOK output. Towards the latter, an optical VLC link budget of 33 dB has been found compatible at 100 Mb/s rate and real-time Ethernet-over-VLC transmission has been demonstrated over a 100-m out-door link for LiDAR point-cloud data exchange. Higher rates towards 1 Gb/s have been evaluated through use of either a visible LD or an excessively equalized medium-flux LED. While the former benefits from its collimated light emission and can further support data rates up to 10 Gb/s by means of OFDM, the latter faces a greatly reduced compatible link budget due to practical limitations for the RF drive of the LED and a reduced optical modulation amplitude at frequencies approaching 1 GHz. Nevertheless, VLC applications where LEDs are used in a rate-adaptive manner are thinkable.

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